

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Regional Health Interventions: A Comparative Analysis of the Trend in Anaemia Case Reduction across Districts in Greater Accra, Ghana

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ABSTRACT

Background

Anaemia in pregnant women is a public health issue, particularly in developing countries including Ghana, and pregnant women and children are mostly affected. Preceding trend analysis has not been conducted among pregnant women with anaemia in Greater Accra. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the trend in anaemia case reduction and the effectiveness of Regional Health Interventions across Districts in Greater Accra.

Methods

The study was conducted in all 29 Districts in the Greater Accra Region. It utilized datasets from 2018 to 2022 of the District Health Information Management System from the Ghana Health Service. The data were restricted to pregnant women with anaemia at 36 weeks of pregnancy, whose haemoglobin levels were recorded. The sample sizes from 2018 to 2022 were 23513, 23691, 26297, 24148 and 22079 respectively. The data were analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 to describe anaemia prevalence from 2018 to 2022. Analysis of variance for anaemia prevalence between years and within years was also determined. Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) posthoc test of anaemia prevalence to identify the mean statistical differences every year.

Results

Findings from the study revealed an increased level of anaemia prevalence in 2019 (54.5%) and the lowest figure in 2021 (45.2%). Over the years, the mean prevalence of anaemia in pregnant women has reduced. The gradual decline in anaemia prevalence may be due to intervention programmes put in place by the Ghana Health Service and non-governmental organizations (NGOs,) to reduce anaemia in pregnant women. The significant difference in the prevalence of anaemia over the years was due to the prevalence in 2022.

Conclusion

This study emphasized the five-year trend of anaemia in pregnancy at 36 weeks of gestation in all 29 districts in Greater Accra. Discoveries from the study revealed a steady decrease in the prevalence of pregnancy anaemia in the various Districts. Even though there was a decline in the prevalence rate in the study areas, Districts such as Ningo Prampram, Ada East, Ada West, Kpone-Katamanso and Adentan recorded an increase in the prevalence of pregnancy anaemia. Further research work is needed to understand the upsurge in the prevalence of anaemia in pregnancy despite the intervention programmes. Anaemia in pregnant women requires earnest interventions to reduce adverse maternal and perinatal outcomes. Continuous health education and advocacy programmes are required to help reduce anaemia in pregnant women.

Keywords: Health interventions, trend in pregnancy anaemia, pregnant women, and anaemia.

1. Introduction

Anaemia is a global health crisis especially in low- and middle-income countries with about a 60% prevalence rate. The cause of anaemia is complex, with iron deficiency at paramount and very common in expectant mothers. Iron is the basic requirement for the development of red blood cells and about 80% of the available heme iron is used for haemoglobin development in erythroblasts.(Costa & de Paula Ayres-Silva, 2023a; Sun et al., 2021). Ayele et al. (2023) define pregnancy anaemia as a haemoglobin level of less than 11 grams per deciliter, and it is the cardinal factor that contributes to maternal morbidity and mortality, particularly in developing countries. Although there are numerous causes of anaemia, iron-deficiency anaemia is the commonest type and it occurs when a person is not able to take in enough iron in the diet or due to blood loss. (Paul et al., 2021). Pernicious and B12 deficiency anaemia is caused by a lack of vitamin B12, vital for the formation of strong red blood cells. Complications of certain disease conditions and food with smaller amounts of vitamin B12 can result in Pernicious and B12 deficiency anaemia. Another name for pernicious anaemia is megaloblastic anaemia, consequently, the synthesis of the red blood cells formed is bigger than normal. When the bone marrow stops to function and produces inadequate red blood cells than the body demands it is termed aplastic anaemia. When the red blood cells are damaged early in lifespan and the body is deficient in the right quantity to function

is called Haemolytic anaemia. Chronic illnesses such as chronic kidney disease, heart failure, and cancers can also result in anaemia (Australia, 2023; (Trivedi et al., 2024) Nonetheless, anaemia continues to significantly impact health in low and middle-income countries, and Ghana is no exception. Although helpful strategies have been instituted by the Ghana Health Service and NGOs, anaemia still causes health problems during pregnancy. Efforts have been made at the District, Municipal and Metropolitan levels to decrease the anaemia prevalence rate in pregnant women, by strengthening health education on early detection and treatment of anaemia in pregnancy, nutrition counselling in pregnancy and the use of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs). Although all these measures are in place, most health facilities still record an upsurge of anaemia cases in pregnant women.

Even though anaemia in pregnant women was initially studied in different Districts in Greater Accra, it was just limited to specified communities and facilities. Additionally, this preceding trend analysis has not been conducted in Greater Accra. Therefore, the study seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of regional health interventions on the trend in anaemia case reduction across Districts in Greater Accra, Ghana, by using a five-year (2018-2022) trend of anaemia cases at 36weeks of pregnancy in Twenty-nine (29) Districts in Greater Accra Region. Source data from the District Health Information Management System (DHIMS-2) were used.

2. Definitions of Anaemia

Anaemia is a health condition which exhibits a decline in red blood cells or a reduction in the production of adequate red blood cells, due to blood loss, or increased red blood cell breakdown. Undertaken that red blood cells transport haemoglobin (Hb), an important protein for oxygen passage, minimal red blood cells result in inadequate oxygen delivery to vital organs and tissues causing anaemia.(Brittenham et al., 2023) Lugthart et al., 2020).

Anaemia occurs when insufficient red blood cells are formed in the body, as such the haemoglobin level decreases and alters the oxygen-carrying capacity. The World Health Organization (WHO) endorse the reference values of HB lower than 11g/dL in children 6-59 months, below 11.5g/dL in children 5 to 11 years, below 11.0g/dL in expectant mothers, below 12.0g/dL in children 12 to14 years, lower than 12.0g/dL in females who are not pregnant, and below 13.0g/dL in males. The reference values were proposed by WHO in 1958 and revised and updated in 1968. Haemoglobin reference values for distinguishing anaemia differ between men and women, and children and expectant mothers. Predictors that affect the classification of anaemia include medical, genetic, and nutritional disorders. WHO thus suggest other studies with detailed explanations to define anaemia to amend universal guidelines.(Braat et al., 2023; Sandin et al., 2023). The complete blood count is the process of determining distinctive elements in the circulating blood (haemogram). This shows the blood concentration, reduced, or increased relates to the standard value of measurement. The identification and treatment of anaemia depend on medical investigations and diagnosis. To come out with the correct diagnosis, the blood sample

collected is tested with radiological images and other investigations, as well as the patient history to give an appropriate treatment.(Yagmur et al., 2024) (Saputra et al., 2023)

For a standard anaemia diagnosis, verified threshold values for haemoglobin and haematocrit levels are required, with interpretations indicating anaemia. These values differ across regions, because of the impact of many physiological factors on the haemoglobin levels. The WHO gives clear threshold values for diagnosing and the management of anaemia, depending on the haemoglobin and haematocrit levels, and these are carefully summarized in Table 1. (Mireku et al., 2016).

Table 1: Haemoglobin and haematocrit levels for diagnosing anaemia.

Category	Haemoglobin (g/L)	Haematocrit (%)
Children 6 months to 59 months	110	33
Children 5 to 11 years	115	34
Children 12 to 14 years	120	36
Non-pregnant women > 15 years	120	36
Pregnant women	110	33
Men > 15 years	130	39

(Mireku et al., 2016)

3. Predictors of Anaemia

Anaemia in pregnancy is an essential predictor of negative outcomes in pregnancy including small for age, preterm birth, miscarriages, low Apgar score, and perinatal death. Anaemic pregnant women are most likely to suffer maternal illnesses like miscarriages, antepartum and postpartum haemorrhages, as well as preeclampsia. The triggers of pregnancy anaemia are complex. Heightened dietary and micronutrient requirements are correlated with anaemia in pregnancy, worm infections, malaria, and terminal diseases also cause pregnancy anaemia. (Geta et al., 2022). The indicators of socio-demographic factors, including the size of the family, location, marital status, and education level of women have a correlation with anaemia in pregnancy. (Hailu et al., 2019; Belay et al., 2023). The implications of reproductive factors in identifying anaemia in

pregnancy include pregnancy age, birth spacing, antenatal clinic follow-up, antepartum haemorrhage, and severe menorrhagia is known considerably to be related to anaemia. For example, birth spacing below 2 years displays greater chances of getting anaemia as compared with birth spacing of more than 2 years. (Geta et al.'s 2022; Alam, 2023). Additionally, pregnant women in their 3rd trimester have higher chances of developing anaemia compared with those in their 1st and 2nd trimesters of gestation. Triggers of anaemia in such situations include the history of inadequate ANC visits and postpartum haemorrhage (Bissa et al., 2024; Geta et al., 2022). Emphasis on nutritional factors, which play a critical function in predicting anaemia in pregnancy, include folic acid and iron supplementation, alongside sufficient dietary diversity. Paying less attention to the consumption of iron-folic acid in pregnancy increases the possibility of anaemia. (Konlan et al., 2023). Moreover, Socio-economic factors such as harmful lifestyles, and various cultures and traditions are linked to the contributing factors of increased anaemia cases in pregnant women, especially in South Saharan Africa. Social determining factors of health, together with education and employment, are triggers of anaemia in pregnant women in Ghana. (Tettegah et al., 2024).

For the study of predictors of anaemia, figure 1 below illustrates the categorization of these factors into 3 levels thus direct, indirect, and distant correlation to anaemia in pregnancy. This approach allows for the assessment and verification of the classification of these factors into the recommended hierarchical levels.(Demétrio et al., 2017).

Figure 1: Categorization framework of the predictors of anaemia in pregnancy.

(Demétrio et al., 2017)

4. Trends in pregnancy anaemia

There is a prevailing phenomenon of high level of occurrence of anaemia among women in Greater Accra. Data from the Ghana Health Service indicate a National Five-year trend of anaemia in pregnancy from 2018 to 2022 were 34.5, 35.6, 34.7%, 33.1% and 31.4%. In 2022, Ningo Prampram, Ada East, Ada West, Kpone-Katamanso, and Adentan recorded 51.6%, 45.1%, 42.7%, 39.3 % and 38.5% respectively, indicative of anaemia in pregnancy exceeding the target of 35.5%. Together, the above issue continues to pose a lot of challenges to various district health directorates because the development appears to defy reason because the pregnant women who were found to be anaemic at 36 weeks of pregnancy have virtually all been receiving antenatal care (ANC) at various health facilities, therefore one does not expect such ANC-attending expectant mothers to be anaemic at no less a time than 36 weeks of pregnancy. Regular attendance at ANC, in theory, should lead to early detection and treatment of anaemia, so it is unexpected for a pregnant woman to have anaemia at 36 weeks or later if she is regularly attending ANC. Twenty-nine districts in the Greater Accra Region appear to be susceptible to the aforementioned trend, although in 2022, it was 5 districts namely Ningo Prampram, Ada East, Ada West, Kpone-Katamanso, and Adentan, who reported the highest proportions of anaemia in pregnant women at 36 weeks of pregnancy.

5. Materials and methods

Data source and study area

The study was carried out in all 29 Districts in Greater Accra Region, Ghana. It employed datasets from 2018 to 2022. The main source data is from the District Health Information Management System (DHIMS-2) in the Ghana Health Service. The data were limited to pregnant women with anaemia at 36 weeks of pregnancy, whose haemoglobin levels were recorded. The sample sizes from 2018 to 2022 were 23513, 23691, 26297, 24148 and 22079 respectively.

Data analysis

Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 was used to analyze and describe anaemia prevalence from 2018 to 2022. Analysis of variance for anaemia prevalence between years and within years was also determined. Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) posthoc test of anaemia prevalence to identify the means of statistical difference every year.

Results

Table 2: Description of Anaemia prevalence at 36weeks of gestation

Year	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean
2018	29	10.80	50.10	32.3276
2019	29	14.00	54.50	31.9276
2020	29	4.10	53.80	31.6172
2021	29	2.10	45.20	26.2345
2022	29	2.60	51.60	25.4483
Total	145	2.10	54.50	29.5110

The study was made up of 29 Districts assessed over 5 years for the prevalence of anaemia at 36 weeks of gestation. The highest level of anaemia prevalence was seen in 2019 (54.5%) while the lowest was also realized in 2021 (45.2%). Largely the mean prevalence of pregnancy anaemia among women attending ANC within the Districts decreases as the year increases.

Table 3: Analysis of variance for anaemia prevalence in pregnancy

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1318.067	4	329.517	2.816	.028
Within Groups	16384.435	140	117.032		
Total	17702.502	144			

Table 4: Multiple Comparisons for anaemia in pregnancy (posthoc test)

	(I) Year	(J) Year	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Games-Howell	2018	2019	.40000	2.52310	1.000	-6.7137	7.5137
		2020	.71034	2.63991	.999	-6.7377	8.1584
		2021	6.09310	2.80920	.208	-1.8437	14.0299
		2022	6.87931	2.76121	.108	-.9185	14.6771

	2019	2018	-40000	2.52310	1.000	-7.5137	6.7137
		2020	.31034	2.74828	1.000	-7.4377	8.0584
		2021	5.69310	2.91128	.301	-2.5215	13.9077
		2022	6.47931	2.86500	.173	-1.6023	14.5610
	2020	2018	-71034	2.63991	.999	-8.1584	6.7377
		2019	-.31034	2.74828	1.000	-8.0584	7.4377
		2021	5.38276	3.01307	.392	-3.1129	13.8784
		2022	6.16897	2.96838	.244	-2.1993	14.5373
	2021	2018	-6.09310	2.80920	.208	-14.0299	1.8437
		2019	-5.69310	2.91128	.301	-13.9077	2.5215
		2020	-5.38276	3.01307	.392	-13.8784	3.1129
		2022	.78621	3.11990	.999	-8.0079	9.5803
	2022	2018	-6.87931	2.76121	.108	-14.6771	.9185
		2019	-6.47931	2.86500	.173	-14.5610	1.6023
		2020	-6.16897	2.96838	.244	-14.5373	2.1993
		2021	-.78621	3.11990	.999	-9.5803	8.0079

The study found that there was a significant difference in the prevalence of anaemia at 36 weeks of pregnancy over the years as seen in (table 3). The significant difference was attributed to the prevalence in 2022 as indicated in (table 4).

6. Discussion

The study aimed to evaluate the trend in anaemia case reduction and the effectiveness of Regional Health Interventions across Districts in Greater Accra. The study was made up of all the 29 districts in Greater Accra and measured 5 years for the prevalence of anaemia. Findings indicated the highest level of anaemia prevalence in 2019 (54.5%) and the lowest figure recorded in 2021 (45.2%). The mean prevalence of pregnancy anaemia among women attending antenatal care in the various Districts reduces as the year increases. The steady decline in the anaemia rate among pregnant women in most of the districts may be attributed to the effective measures put in place by the Ghana Health Service and NGOs, to reduce anaemia in pregnant women. Also, efforts were made at the district levels to reduce anaemia in pregnancy by intensifying health education on early detection and management of anaemia, nutrition education during pregnancy and the use of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs). Furthermore, the study realized a significant variation in the anaemia prevalence over the five years in the study areas. The significant difference in the anaemia prevalence over the years was due to the prevalence in 2022. Findings also indicated that anaemia prevalence among expectant mothers generally decreases from year to year. Even though there was a decline in the anaemia prevalence of among pregnant women in the study areas, districts such as Ningo Prampram, Ada East, Ada West, Kpone-Katamanso and Adentan recorded a rise in anaemia prevalence among pregnant women.

7. Conclusion

Pregnancy anaemia is a health problem in most developing countries including Ghana. The increased prevalence rate is due to triggers such as infections, ineffective antenatal services, poor dietary choices, and lifestyle. The effects of pregnancy anaemia are detrimental to the pregnant mother and foetus. To lessen the effect of anaemia in pregnant women in Ghana, rigorous strategies are needed to tackle the root causes of anaemia in pregnancy. Considering their nutrition, economic status, education, culture, and belief systems. Furthermore, intervention programmes should be tailored to address their basic needs. To promote and improve the health outcomes of expectant mothers and children, collaborative efforts are needed involving health service providers, stakeholders, community members and the government, by prioritizing the delivery of accessible and comprehensive antenatal care services, and intervention programmes intended to lessen poverty and improve the socioeconomic status of women. In general, to reduce the effect of anaemia in pregnancy in Ghana a thorough approach that will focus on the fundamental factors leading to anaemia in pregnancy anaemia. Further studies are required to understand the increase in the anaemia prevalence in pregnancy despite the availability of intervention programmes. Pregnancy anaemia needs urgent intervention to reduce adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes. Continuous health education and advocacy programmes are needed to help reduce anaemia in pregnancy.

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